

Replication of Ataguba et al. (2023): Income Inequality and COVID-19 Mortality

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Release date: 17/10/2025

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19496554>

Context

Pandemics not only affect health but also exacerbate socioeconomic disparities. A growing body of evidence shows that inequality amplifies the incidence and mortality of diseases such as HIV and COVID-19. Poverty, while related, is conceptually distinct and has received less systematic attention. In their 2023 BMJ Global Health paper, Ataguba et al. demonstrated that income inequality (measured by the Gini index) is positively and significantly associated with HIV incidence, AIDS mortality (t+1), and COVID-19 excess mortality, after controlling for health expenditure, income group, and regional fixed effects. Effects were particularly strong for HIV incidence in Africa, while the COVID-19 association was not significant in Africa alone.

As a first step for addressing the Inequality Council's questions, we replicated the Ataguba model using updated datasets (2020–2022) and expanded coverage. This replication provides the methodological baseline before addressing three key questions: substitution of poverty for inequality, inequalities in vaccine access, and reverse causality between pandemics and inequalities.

Methods and Data

The model is as follows:

$$COVID_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 Gini_{i,t} + HEX_{i,t} + Income_{i,t} + Region_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

where COVID represent Covid-19 excess mortality -19 excess mortality), Gini is income inequality, and X is a set of controls (health expenditure per capita, income group, and UNAIDS region). Key dataset differences from Ataguba et al. (2023):

Table 1 :Key differences between COVID-19 dataset

	Ataguba et al. (2023)	Updated COVID-19 dataset	Difference (number)	(%)
Total observations	322	573	251	78%
Africa observations	106	198	92	87%
Non-Africa observations	216	375	159	74%
Unique countries	107-123	192	85-69	79%-56%

This broader coverage strengthens statistical robustness, particularly for Africa.

Results of the 2025 model

Table 2 presents the regression results on COVID-19 excess mortality. Individual regressions are available in Supplementary Material S1.

Table 2 : Ataguba (2023) replication with updated COVID-19 data

Model specification	Obs. (N)	Countries (N)	β (Gini)	SE	95% CI lower	upper bound	<i>p</i> - value
Global (incl. Africa)	573	192	152.08	140.7 3	-125.71	429.8 7	0.284
Global (excl. Africa)	435	146	85.34	176.9 0	-262.37	433.0 4	0.630
Africa only	138	46	331.15	145.2 1	46.55	615.7 6	0.024

The global sample now covers 192 countries and 573 observations and the Africa region, 46 countries and 138 observations. The results for the global and non-African samples are weaker and became non-significant, reflecting dilution of Africa's strong effect when combined with non-African countries.

Discussion: Africa at the Centre of the Inequality–Pandemic Nexus

Our replication confirms that inequality has a particularly strong and statistically significant association with COVID-19 excess mortality in Africa. This is not a statistical curiosity, nor a regional anomaly. Rather, it highlights how Africa has stood at the very centre of global vulnerability during the pandemic(1).

It is important to recall the broader historical and political economy context. The pandemic did not create new inequalities; it magnified those already deeply embedded in the global system(2, 3). Across 2020 and 2021, African leaders, the African Union, and multilateral organisations such as UNAIDS Executive Director, Winnie Byanyima, repeatedly warned of

“deadly inequalities”. While high-income countries have hoarded stocks of masks, ICU equipment, and eventually vaccines, African countries struggled to secure even the most basic supplies. This became widely described as a form of vaccine apartheid(4) an emblematic symbol of the failure of global solidarity.

Inside African countries, structural conditions amplified these external inequities. Models of epidemic spread have shown that in contexts of high inequality and social segregation, low-income groups bear a disproportionate burden of infection and death(5, 6). This is consistent with what we observed in informal settlements across African cities, where overcrowding, limited sanitation, and precarious work made physical distancing impossible(7). The informal economy – where the majority of Africa’s workforce is employed – left millions without social protection, health insurance, or sick leave. For these households, inequality was not an abstract statistic but a daily determinant of survival(8).

The economic shock of COVID-19 also hit Africa harder and differently. Job losses in the informal sector, declining remittances, and falling agricultural and urban incomes all converged to deepen existing gaps. Analyses by the World Inequality Lab showed that, in the Global South, the pandemic functioned as a “distributional recession”, with vulnerable households carrying the heaviest losses. In Africa, these dynamics played out against a backdrop of long-standing structural fragilities: dependence on commodity exports, limited fiscal space, and under-developed manufacturing bases. Historians and economists alike have pointed out that this legacy – rooted in colonial extraction and uneven global integration – left the continent particularly exposed to shocks such as COVID-19.

In this light, our result – that inequality is significantly associated with COVID-19 mortality in Africa but not elsewhere – is neither surprising nor incidental. It is a mirror of broader systemic inequities. Africa’s case illustrates, with statistical clarity, that pandemics strike hardest where inequality and vulnerability intersect.

Policy implications are clear. Any serious agenda for pandemic preparedness must address not only the biomedical dimensions of response but also the structural inequities that shape exposure, resilience, and outcomes. For Africa, this means investing in universal health coverage, expanding social protection systems, and building regional capacity to produce and distribute vaccines and essential medical supplies. Without such steps, the next pandemic risks reproducing – or even deepening – the deadly inequalities we observed during COVID-19.

Take-home messages

- Results show no statistically significant association between the Gini index and COVID-19 excess mortality at the Global level, but a strong positive correlation between inequality and COVID-19 excess deaths in Africa.

- Thanks to the additional country values on COVID-19 data for the years 2020 and 2021, particularly in Africa, our results update and reinforce the central finding of Ataguba et al. (2023): inequality undermines pandemic resilience in Africa. A one decimal change in the Gini index was associated with an increase of 331 excess deaths among African countries ($\beta=331.15$, p -value=.024, 95%CI [145.21 – 46.55
- Our findings demonstrate that the African case is the most compelling and policy-relevant. It reminds us the challenging moment when leaders from the Greater South and UNAIDS Executive Director were raising the alert on the deadly inequalities faced by Africa as the COVID-19 pandemic was unfolding and rich countries were buying redundant quantities of masks, gloves, ICU equipment and redundant quantities of COVID-19 vaccines.

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Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Materials S1: 2025 Results of Ataguba’s model

Table S1.1. Global Estimate (Including Africa)

```
. regress covid gini ln_health_exp_pc i.region_num ///
> if !missing(covid, gini, ln_health_exp_pc, region_num), ///
> vce(robust)
```

```
Linear regression      Number of obs   =      573
                      F(8, 564)           =      21.43
                      Prob > F          =      0.0000
                      R-squared         =      0.2665
                      Root MSE       =     152.15
```

covid	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
gini	152.0825	141.7306	1.07	0.284	-126.3017	430.4668
ln_health_exp_pc	-18.88395	5.463692	-3.46	0.001	-29.61561	-8.152276
region num						
Africa - West and Central	-32.89168	15.02877	-2.19	0.029	-62.41088	-3.372489
Asia and Pacific	11.28163	21.53727	0.52	0.601	-31.02142	53.58468
Eastern Europe and Central Asia	304.4506	45.48168	6.69	0.000	215.1164	393.7847
Latin America and the Caribbean	107.8354	23.09135	4.67	0.000	62.4799	153.191
North Africa and Middle East	40.58794	19.28135	2.11	0.036	2.715916	78.45997
Western and Central Europe and North America	233.0768	43.8777	5.31	0.000	146.8931	319.2604
_cons	104.7033	89.15969	1.17	0.241	-70.42229	279.8289

Table S1.3. Global Estimate (Excluding Africa)

```
. regress covid gini ln_health_exp_pc i.region_num ///
> if africa == 0, vce(robust)
```

```
Linear regression      Number of obs   =      435
                      F(6, 428)           =      21.75
                      Prob > F          =      0.0000
                      R-squared         =      0.2330
                      Root MSE       =     169.27
```

covid	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
gini	85.34119	176.904	0.48	0.630	-262.3676	433.0499
ln_health_exp_pc	-22.76667	6.321825	-3.60	0.000	-35.19235	-10.34098
region num						
Eastern Europe and Central Asia	290.6625	40.80083	7.12	0.000	210.4676	370.8575
Latin America and the Caribbean	105.7126	25.82478	4.09	0.000	54.95345	156.4718
North Africa and Middle East	32.33239	19.09916	1.69	0.091	-5.207445	69.87222
Western and Central Europe and North America	225.4041	32.32102	6.97	0.000	161.8764	288.9318
_cons	174.1278	105.3349	1.65	0.099	-32.91026	381.1659

Table S1.3. Africa Only Estimate

```
. regress covid gini ln health exp_pc ///
> if africa == 1, vce(robust)
```

```
Linear regression                Number of obs   =       138
                                F(2, 135)       =         2.81
                                Prob > F             =       0.0639
                                R-squared            =       0.0557
                                Root MSE         =       75.322
```

covid	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
gini	331.1532	145.2082	2.28	0.024	43.9761	618.3303
ln health exp pc	-5.370978	8.840196	-0.61	0.544	-22.85417	12.11221
_cons	-77.54631	91.43283	-0.85	0.398	-258.3723	103.2797